

Research Article

Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Aprepitant in Bulk and Capsule Formulation

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ABSTRACT

Analytical method development and validation is critical in pharmaceutical discovery, development, and manufacturing. The current study discusses the creation and validation of a UV Spectrophotometric method for Aprepitant. Simple, accurate and cost efficient Spectrophotometric method has been developed for the estimation of Aprepitant in bulk and Capsule dosage form. The standard and sample solutions were produced by utilizing ethanol as solvent. The optimum conditions for the analysis of the drug were established. The maximum wavelength (λ_{max}) was found at 264nm. Beers law was obeyed in the concentration range of 5-15 μ g/mL concentration. The line equation $y = 43.2401x + 0.0013$ with r^2 of 0.998 was obtained. Linearity, accuracy, precision, LoD, and LoQ were validated in accordance with ICH guidelines. The proposed method could be used to analyse Aprepitant in bulk and capsule formulation for quality control purposes.

INTRODUCTION

In conjunction with other antiemetic medications, Aprepitant, an antiemetic and substance p/neurokinin 1 (NK1) receptor antagonist, is suggested for the prevention of acute and delayed nausea and vomiting related to initial and repeat rounds of highly emetogenic cancer chemotherapy. Human substance P/neurokinin 1 (nk1) receptors are selectively and highly

affinitized by Aprepitant. The targets of current treatments for chemotherapy induced nausea and vomiting include serotonin (5-HT₃), dopamine, and corticosteroid receptors. Aprepitant has little to no affinity for these receptors (CINV). [1][2][3]

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Figure A: Chemical Structure of Aprepitant

A review of the literature finds that some research has been done on the HPLC determination of Aprepitant in plasma and pharmaceutical formulations. To the best of our knowledge, no UV approach for analyzing Aprepitant in pharmaceutical formulations has been published in the literature [4][5][6][7]. The goal of this project is to develop and validate a rapid, simple, reliable, selective, sensitive, and low-cost UV Spectrophotometric method for determining Aprepitant in bulk drugs and commercial pharmaceutical formulations like capsules.

Drug Profile of Aprepitant [8]

Drug Name: Aprepitant

Category: Anti-emetics

Chemical formula: $C_{23}H_{21}F_7N_4O_3$

IUPAC Name: 5-([(2R, 3S)-2-((R)-1-[3,5-bis(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]ethoxy)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)morpholino]methyl)-1H-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-one

Molecular Weight: 534.427g/mol

Melting point: 251-255°C

Half life: 9-13 Hours

Mechanism of Action

Aprepitant is a highly specific antagonist of the G-protein coupled neurokinin-1 receptor [9][10][11]. Both the central and peripheral nervous systems have neurokinin-1 receptors. Substance P, a nociceptive neurotransmitter, is their major ligand.

The central pattern generator, nucleus tractus solitarius (NTS), and region postrema are hypothesised to play essential roles in the vomiting reflex (Aprepitant). [12][13][14]

Since central neurokinin-1 receptors are located throughout these regions, aprepitant can be widely bound in these crucial areas. Aprepitant is anticipated to dramatically reduce the chance of the complicated vomiting reflex beginning by acting as a competitive antagonist in these locations. [15] Neurokinin-1 (NK-1) receptors can be found throughout the gastrointestinal system. The Aprepitant's binding to NK-1 receptors may decrease vagal afferent impulses, contributing to the antiemetic action. The proposed mechanism for the antipruritic action is antagonism of substance P, an endogenous NK1 receptor ligand.

Pharmacokinetics

Absorption: Aprepitant has a nonlinear pharmacokinetic profile. The Aprepitant's bioavailability declines with increasing dose, with the mean oral bioavailability being 67% for the 80 mg Aprepitant capsules and 59% for the 125 mg Aprepitant capsules. T max (time to peak plasma concentration) is about four hours. [16]

Distribution: Aprepitant has a high plasma protein binding (about 95%) and a high volume of distribution (V_{ss}) of 70 L at steady state.

Metabolism: Aprepitant is metabolised in the liver via P450 CYP3A4 and CYP2C9, as well as CYP1A2 (minor) and CYP2C19 (minor). Main metabolites are N- and O-dealkylation products which are pharmacologically inactive. It is critical to understand that Aprepitant is both a dose-dependent inhibitor and inducer of CYP3A4. [17]

Excretion: Aprepitant metabolites are eliminated roughly 50% in urine and 50% in faeces.

ICH Guidelines (ICH Q2R1) for Analytical Procedure and Validation [18]

The analytical procedure refers to the manner of performing the analysis. It should detail the steps required to execute each analytical test. This includes, but is not limited to, the preparation of the sample, the reference standard, and the reagents, the use of the apparatus, the development of the calibration curve, the application of the formula for the calculation, and so on.

The subject of analytical procedure validation focuses on the four most frequent types of analytical procedures:

- ✓ Identification examinations
- ✓ Quantitative tests for impurity content - Limit tests for impurity control
- ✓ Quantitative analyses of the active moiety in drug substance or drug product samples, or other specified component(s) of the drug product

The analytical procedure's goal should be clearly known because it will govern the validation qualities that must be examined. The following are some typical validation factors to consider:

- Accuracy
- Precision
- Repeatability
- Intermediate Precision
- Specificity
- Detection Limit
- Quantitation Limit
- Linearity
- Range

Moreover, revalidation may be required in the following situations:

- ✓ Modifications in the manufacture of the medicinal ingredient

- ✓ Changes in the finished product's composition
- ✓ Changes in the analytical procedure

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Aprepitant was procured from Piramal Pharma Limited, Telangana. All the reagents were of analytical grade. The commercially available two marketed tablet brand containing Aprepitant, 125mg and 80mg in each tablet have been used for estimation.

Preparation of Standard stock solution

Weigh accurately and transfer about 80 mg of Aprepitant working standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Add 50ml of Mobile phase. Sonicate for dissolve and makeup with the volume with mobile phase and mix.

Further take 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase. Filter it through 0.45-micron syringe filter.

Preparation of sample solution:

Take equivalent to one capsule(i.e., 80 mg equivalent of Aprepitant) into 100 ml volumetric flask add 50ml of Mobile phase and keep the flask in sonicator for 30 minutes make up the volume up to mark with mobile phase and mix.

Further take 5 ml of this solution in 50ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase. Filter it through 0.45-micron syringe filter.

Validation of method

The method was validated with respect to linearity and range, accuracy and limit of detection (LoD), limit of quantification (LoQ).

Linearity and range

The prepared aliquots (5-15µg/mL) were scanned for absorbance at λ_{max} Value 264nm. The absorbance range was found to be 0.1171-0.3513. These solution obeyed Beer-Lambert's law in above concentration range with regression of 1.0000

Accuracy

The standard solution, Accuracy -80%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -120% solutions were injected. The amount found and amount added for Aprepitant mean recovery values were calculated and the results were summarized.

Limit of Detection (LoD) and Limit of Quantification (LoQ)

LoD (k =3.3) and LoQ (k =10) of the method was established according to ICH definition($C1 =ks/s$, where C1 is LoD or LoQ, S is the mean standard deviation of blank determination, Sis the slope of standard curve and k is the constant related to confidence interval).LoD and LoQ of method reported.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

ABSORBANCE MAXIMA

Figure B: UV Spectrum of Aprepitant in Sample solution

Discussion: The maximum absorbance obtained by 264 nm.

Figure C: Linearity curve for Aprepitant

Table1: Result for Linearity

Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance
5.06	0.1171
7.60	0.1756
10.13	0.2342
12.66	0.2928
15.19	0.3513

Discussion: Five linear concentrations of Aprepitant were absorbed in a duplicate manner. Average absorbance were mentioned above and linearity equations obtained for Aprepitant $y = 43.2401x + 0.0013$. Correlation coefficient obtained $R^2 = 0.998$ for the Aprepitant.

Table 2: Result for Accuracy of Aprepitant

% Recovery Level	Sample wt. (mg)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery	SD	%RSD
80%	15.36	100.37	100.12	0.516	0.52
	15.41	100.15			
	15.33	100.51			
100%	19.63	99.18			
	19.52	99.78			
	19.36	100.39			
120%	22.65	100.92			
	23.20	99.67			
	23.02	100.12			

Discussion: Three levels of Accuracy samples were prepared by standard addition method. The sample absorbance was taken for each level of accuracy and mean %Recovery was obtained as 99.18% and 100.92% for Aprepitant.

ASSAY

Label Claim: Each capsule contains

Aprepitant : 80mg
 Average of net content : 152.00 mg
 Standard Dilution:
 Name of standard : Aprepitant
 Purity of standard : 99.00%
 Standard absorbance : 0.2368
 Sample absorbance : 0.2354

Content in mg

$$\frac{0.2354}{0.2368} \times \frac{10.26}{100} \times \frac{5}{50} \times \frac{100}{19.21} \times \frac{50}{5} \times \frac{99.00}{100.00} \times 152.00$$

$$= 79.896\text{mg}$$

Discussion: Assay was performed with the above formulation. The percentage Assay for Aprepitant 99.87 %.

CONCLUSION:

The UV-Visible Spectrophotometer analytical method was simple, reliable, accurate, and

reproducible. The main characteristics of this method are its low cost, faster speed, satisfactory precision, and good specificity in assessing the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present. The method was validated successfully according to ICH guidelines and can be used for routine quality control analysis of Aprepitant in bulk drug and Capsule formulations without interference from excipient.

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